

Studies on Thioureas—III

Preparation of 2-*p*-Chlorophenylsulphophenylamino-4-Arylamino-*s*-Triazine-6-yl-Thioureas/Phenylthioureas

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2-4-Disubstituted-*s*-triazine-6-yl-thioureas and phenylthioureas containing aminodiphenyl sulphone moiety have been prepared. Their constitution has been supported by uv as well as ir spectra. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

THIOUREA derivatives possess antitubercular¹, antithyroid², hypnotic and anaesthetic³, anthelmintic⁴, antibacterial⁵, antispasmodic⁶ and possible anticonvulsant activity⁷. *s*-Triazine derivative and sulphones also show therapeutic activity⁸. As few *s*-triazinyl thiourea derivatives are available in literature⁹, we have prepared *s*-triazinyl thioureas of type (I) having aminodiphenylsulphone moiety.

The first chlorine of cyanuric chloride was condensed with *p*-amino-*p*'-chloro diphenylsulphone at 0^o1⁰. The second and third chlorine atoms of cyanuric chloride were replaced by arylamine at 35-40^o and ammonia at 80^o respectively leading to the formation of 2-(*p*'-chlorophenyl-*p*-sulphophenyl)-amino-4-arylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazines. Amino group of the above compound was reacted with ammoniumthiocyanate and phenyl isothiocyanate to get thiourea and phenylthiourea respectively. Constitution of product was supported by uv and ir spectra.

UV and IR spectra study :

The UV spectra of thiourea and phenylthiourea were taken using ethanol as solvent. The bands were observed at 215 to 220 mμ and 280 to 300 mμ. Infrared spectra of thiourea and phenylthiourea

were taken on KBr pellet. Vibration frequency for both the compounds except NH broad band in thiourea derivative. The above product gave C₃N₃ frequency at 810 cm⁻¹, SO₂ band at 1145-50 cm⁻¹, C=S band 1110 cm⁻¹ and NH band between 3200 to 3500 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

(1) *Preparation of 2-(p'-chlorophenyl-p-sulphophenyl)-amino 4, 6-dichloro-s-triazine :*

It was prepared by condensing cyanuric chloride (0.01 mole) with *p*-amino-*p*'-chlorodiphenylsulphone (0.01 mole) at 0^o1⁰. The product was crystallised from ethanol. Yield 75%, m.p. 275d. (Found C, 38.18; H, 1.94; N, 20.18%. Calculated for C₁₅H₉O₂N₄Cl₂S, C, 38.16; N 1.92; N 20.20%.)

(2) *Preparation of 2-(p'-chlorophenyl-p-sulphophenyl) amino-4-arylamino-6-chloro-s-triazine :*

2-(*p*'-Chlorophenyl-*p*-sulphophenyl)-amino-4-6-dichloro-*s*-triazine (0.01 mole) was condensed with aniline (0.01 mole) at 30-40^o using dioxane (40 ml) as solvent¹⁰. The product obtained was isolated and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 90%, m.p. 179-80^o. (Found C, 55.7; H, 3.77; N, 18.50%. Calculated for C₂₁H₁₅O₂Cl₂N₃S, C, 55.68; H, 3.78; N, 18.00%.) Similarly other bases were condensed. Physical constants are recorded in table 1.

(3) *Preparation of 2-(p'-chlorophenyl-p-sulphophenyl)-amino 4-arylamino-6-amino-s-triazine :*

2-(*p*'-chlorophenyl-*p*-sulphophenyl)-amino-4-arylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (0.01 mole) was condensed with liq. ammonia using dioxane (20 ml) as solvent at 70-80^o. The product obtained was isolated and crystallised from ethanol. Physical constants are recorded in Table 1.

(4) *Preparation of 2-(p'-chlorophenyl-p-sulphophenyl)-amino-4-arylamino-s-triazine-6-yl-thiourea :*

A mixture of 2-(*p*'-chlorophenyl-*p*-sulphophenyl)-amino-4-arylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazine (0.01 mole),

conc. hydrochloric acid (2 ml) and ammonium ethanol¹¹. Other thiourea derivatives were prepared as above. Physical constants are recorded in Table 2. Product was isolated and crystallised from Table 2.

TABLE 1—2-(p'-CHLOROPHENYL-p-SULPHOPHENYL)-AMINO-4-ARYL-6-CHLORO/AMINO-S-TRIAZINE

Sl. No.	Cl/or Amino	Aryl	Formula	Yield in%	m.p. °C	N in %	
						Cal.	Obtained
1.	Chloro	Phenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	90	179-80	14.40	14.30
2.	"	o-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ Cl ₃ N ₆ S	88	169-70	13.44	13.35
3.	"	m-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ Cl ₃ N ₆ S	87	154-55	13.44	13.35
4.	"	p-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ Cl ₃ N ₆ S	85	176-77	13.44	13.35
5.	"	o-Tolyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	89	190-01	14.00	13.95
6.	"	m-Tolyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	88	183-84	14.00	13.95
7.	"	p-Tolyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	85	192-93	14.00	13.95
8.	"	o-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	92	209-10	15.80	15.75
9.	"	p-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	90	200-01	15.80	15.75
10.	"	o-Anisyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₃ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	83	144-45	13.56	13.50
11.	"	p-Anisyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₃ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	85	194-95	13.56	13.50
12.	"	p-Iodophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ Cl ₂ IN ₆ S	80	174-75	11.41	11.40
13.	"	Sulphonamido-phenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ S ₂	87	168-69	12.80	12.75
14.	"	α-Naphthyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	52	148-49	11.11	11.10
15.	Amino	Phenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ ClN ₆ S	74	180-81	13.00	13.05
16.	"	o-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	76	220-21	16.77	16.79
17.	"	m-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	74	145-46	16.77	16.79
18.	"	p-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	78	135-36	16.77	16.79
19.	"	o-Tolyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ ClN ₆ S	71	160-61	17.46	17.48
20.	"	m-Tolyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ ClN ₆ S	68	159-60	17.46	17.48
21.	"	p-Tolyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ ClN ₆ S	70	174-75	17.46	17.48
22.	"	o-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₄ ClN ₆ S	78	274-75	19.15	19.17
23.	"	p-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₄ ClN ₆ S	80	269-70	19.15	19.17
24.	"	o-Anisyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₃ ClN ₆ S	69	164-65	19.92	19.94
25.	"	p-Anisyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₃ ClN ₆ S	74	169-70	19.92	19.94
26.	"	Sulphanamido-phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₄ ClN ₆ S ₂	81	219-20	15.35	15.37
27.	"	p-Iodophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ ClIN ₆ S	73	164-65	14.17	14.19
28.	"	α-Naphthyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ ClN ₆ S	72	154-55	13.15	13.17

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF THIOUREAS AND PHENYL THIOUREAS OF TYPE I

Sl. No.	R	R'	Formula	Yield in%	m.p. °C	N in %	
						Cal.	Obtained
1.	H	Phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ ClN ₇ S ₂	67	180-81	18.59	18.55
2.	"	o-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₇ S ₂	70	194-95	17.45	17.50
3.	"	m-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₇ S ₂	68	190-01	17.45	17.50
4.	"	p-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₇ S ₂	69	182-83	17.45	17.50
5.	"	o-Tolyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₇ ClS ₂	85	179-80	18.11	18.15
6.	"	m-Tolyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₇ ClS ₂	63	174-75	18.11	18.15
7.	"	p-Tolyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₇ ClS ₂	66	189-90	18.11	18.15
8.	"	o-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₇ ClS ₂	70	204-05	19.56	19.60
9.	"	p-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₇ ClS ₂	69	184-85	19.56	19.60
10.	"	o-Anisyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₇ ClS ₂	67	185-86	12.56	12.60
11.	"	p-Anisyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₇ ClS ₂	68	197-98	12.56	12.60
12.	"	p-Iodophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₇ ClIS ₂	64	169-70	10.70	10.75
13.	"	Sulphonamido-phenyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₇ ClS ₂	66	159-60	11.46	11.50
14.	"	α-Naphthyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ ClN ₇ S ₂	66	184-85	10.43	10.45
15.	"	Phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₂ ClN ₇ S ₂	66	52-53	18.72	18.75
16.	"	o-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₇ S ₂	60	71-72	17.56	17.60
17.	"	m-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₇ S ₂	61	57-68	17.56	17.60
18.	"	p-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₇ S ₂	59	55-56	17.56	17.60
19.	Phenyl	o-Tolyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₂ ClN ₇ S ₂	66	55-56	18.19	18.25
20.	"	m-Tolyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₂ ClN ₇ S ₂	65	57-58	18.19	18.25
21.	"	p-Tolyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₂ ClN ₇ S ₂	63	64-65	18.19	18.25
22.	"	m-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₄ ClN ₇ S ₂	65	88-69	19.71	19.75
23.	"	p-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₄ ClN ₇ S ₂	63	59-60	19.71	19.70
24.	"	o-Anisyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₃ ClN ₇ S ₂	60	61-62	17.72	17.75
25.	"	p-Anisyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₃ ClN ₇ S ₂	61	69-70	17.72	17.75
26.	"	p-Iodophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₂ ClIN ₇ S ₂	63	59-60	15.08	15.10
27.	"	Sulphonamido-phenyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₇ ClS ₂	64	61-62	16.11	16.15
28.	"	α-Naphthyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ ClN ₇ S ₂	61	49-50	14.63	14.65

(5) Preparation of 2-(*p*'-chlorophenyl-*p*-sulphophenyl)-amino-4-arylamino-*s*-triazine-yl-phenylthiourea :

A mixture of 2-(*p*'-chlorophenyl-*p*-sulphophenyl)-amino-4-arylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazine (0.01 mole), phenylisothiocyanate (0.01 mole) and ethanol (35 ml) was refluxed at 70-80° for an hour^{1,2}. Product was isolated after dilution with ice water and crystallised from ethanol. Similarly other *s*-triazine derivatives were condensed with phenylisothiocyanate. Physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

Antimicrobial Screening :

All thiourea and phenylthiourea were tested for antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* using cup-plate method^{1,3}. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 10 mg/ml using dimethyl-formamide as solvent. From the experimental data, it was observed that all the products are moderately active against Gram positive bacteria like *S. aureus* and Gram negative bacteria like *E. coli*. *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenyl and *p*-tolyl derivatives were found to be more active as compared to other derivatives.

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